

Assessment of Genetic Divergence in Linseed (*Linum Usitatissimum L.*) Using Germination Related Traits Under Normal and Salt Stress Condition

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Abstract

An investigation was carried out to assess genetic diversity among 29 linseed genotypes based on germination and early seedling growth related traits under control and salinity stress. The germination test was performed in Petri dishes containing 2-ply filter paper discs. The filter paper was soaked with 10 ml distilled water (control) or NaCl solution at 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹. Data on germination percentage, mean daily germination (%), germination initial time, and maximum germination time and germination duration time in days, seedling fresh and dry weights (g), seedling root and shoot lengths (cm), and seedling vigor index (SVI) were studied. Analysis of variance indicated highly significant differences among the genotypes for all the traits indicating the presence of adequate variability and the possibility to undertake cluster analysis. High levels of genotypic variation for the most basic variability parameters of the different genotypes were recorded under control as well as salinity stress. Close association between phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variability was recorded, which signified the existence of sufficient variability among the genotypes. Based on results of Principal component and Cluster analyses for eight traits studied, 29 genotypes were classified in to six non-overlapping clusters under normal as well as salinity stress conditions elucidating considerable amount of genetic diversity in the genotypes. Under control, cluster I and in saline condition cluster III contained the highest number of 9 genotypes each. Under control, the maximum inter-cluster distance (20.79) was noticed between clusters I and VI followed by the distance between cluster V and VI (15.29). Under salinity stress, the highest inter-cluster distance (25.99) was observed between cluster I and VI followed by the distance between clusters V and VI. The results suggested that genotypes within most distantly related clusters could be used as parents in hybridization program to develop desirable linseed variety.

Keywords: *Salinity stress, germination, seedling growth, genetic diversity, linseed genotype.*

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Introduction

Salinity is one of the prime constraints for agricultural productivity affecting about 20% arable lands of the world especially in the arid and coastal regions (Yamaguchi and Blumwald, 2005). Vast areas of lands in the coastal regions of Southern and South-Western Bangladesh remain fallow during Rabi (winter) season due to salinity (Ahsan, 2010). Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum* L.), a member of the family *Linaceae* is reported to be a moderately salt tolerant crop (Day, et al., 2015; Dubey et al., 2020). It may be grown successfully in South and South- Western saline areas of Bangladesh but the yield of the presently available varieties is very low. To overcome the problem of poor yield, development of high yielding salt tolerant linseed varieties is necessary through breeding program. The common and widely used approaches to plant breeding are hybridization and subsequent selection. The first step of these approaches is identification of diverse parents for hybridization or selection. Only diverse parents offer great possibility of obtaining desirable segregants in the segregating generations (Moll and Robinson, 1962) because sufficient genetic distance between parents is necessary to obtain transgressive segregation (Joshi et al., 2004).

Available reports on the study of genetic diversity in linseed accessions reveal that the diversity assessment is mainly based on plant growth and yield attributes, and other morphological, physiological and molecular characters recorded from mature plants grown in salt free soil and in normal environment (Kumar and Kumar, 2020; Reddy et al., 2022; Patel et al., 2023; Yadav et al., 2024). Reports on the assessment of genetic diversity of linseed under salt stress conditions are very limited (Srivastava et al., 2009; Samantara et al., 2020). Report on genetic diversity assessment in linseed under stress conditions for germination and early seedling growth characters are not available. However, limited literature on the assessment of genetic diversity of other crops for germination and seedling growth characters under abiotic stress is available. Genetic diversity based on germination and seedling growth has been reported in rice under salinity by Kumar et al. (2020) and in maize under drought condition by Mannan and Begum (2023).

To identify salinity tolerance sources of crop plants, conventional approaches are growing of available germplasm in the salt affected soils and selection of desirable plants. However, selection of a salt tolerant genotype based on germination and seedling growth under controlled conditions is simple, quick, precise and very less time consuming (Kaya et al., 2012). As the germination and seedling stages are the beginning of life cycle, which are the most vulnerable stages of plants. So, it is advisable to study the effects of salinity on germination and seedling growth with a view to develop salt tolerant or resistant crops or crop varieties (Aydinsakir et al., 2015).

Under the above circumstances, the present piece of research was undertaken to assess genetic divergence in some linseed genotypes based on germination and early seedling growth related traits under normal and salinity stress conditions.

Materials and Methods

Selection of Genotypes

Twenty-nine linseed genotypes were included in the experiment. Out of these, 14 genotypes (Neela, BD-7141, BD-7142, BD-7143, BD-7146, BD-10703, BD-10704, BD-10706, BD-10707, BD-10708, BD-10709, BD-10710, BD-10698 and BD-10696) were collected from the Plant Genetic Resource Center (PGRC); and 10 (Lin-303, Lin-503, Lin-703, Lin-803, Lin-1203, Lin-1303, Lin-1403, Lin-1903, Lin-2403 and Lin-1503/2) from ORC, of BRAI, Gazipur, Bangladesh. Two genotypes Chilmari and Lin-S-19 were collected respectively from farmers of Rangpur and Satkhira districts of Bangladesh. Other 3 genotypes (Lin-C-16, Lin-V-18 and Lin-1507/2) were obtained from China, Vietnam and Thailand, respectively. All of the genotypes are suitable for oilseed production. Neela is the only linseed variety recommended for cultivation in Bangladesh and it was included as a check variety.

Germination Test

Germination test was conducted under controlled conditions during *Rabi* (winter) of 2020-2021 in the Laboratory of Oilseed Research Center (ORC), Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BRAI), Gazipur, Bangladesh with a view to assess genetic divergence in linseed genotypes based on germination and early seedling growth traits and to identify salinity tolerant genotypes under salt stress condition. The test was performed using salt free (distilled) water and saline solution prepared by dissolving laboratory grade dried NaCl in distilled water. The levels of salinity maintained in the experiment were 0 (control), 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹. Seeds of selected linseed genotypes were surface-sterilized with 5% chlorox for 10 minutes and rinsed with sterilized distilled water for three times. The surface sterilized seeds were placed on 2-ply filter paper discs (90 mm) in 90 Petri dishes and soaked with sterilized distilled water (control), or NaCl solution in distilled at 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m⁻¹ NaCl solution at 10 ml per dish. Surface sterilized seeds were placed on the filter paper in the dishes at 25 seeds per dish and 4 dishes were used for each genotype. The Petri dishes were carefully sealed with paraffin to prevent evaporation. The dishes were placed on the laboratory desk of the Oilseed research laboratory, BARI at an ambient temperature of 25 to 28°C.

Collection and Analysis of Data

The experiment was checked every day during incubation at a fixed time (12:30 pm) and data on germination initial time (GIT) and number of germinated seeds were recorded for 5 days. Final germination percentage (GP), mean daily germination percentage (MDG), maximum germination time (MGT) and germination duration time (GDT) were computed following standard procedures (Kaya et al., 2019; Hefny et al., 2020). At the end of the germination period, additional 2 days were allowed to grow the seedlings in the same Petri dishes. The seedlings were removed from the Petri dishes and data on shoot length (SL), root length (RL), seedling fresh weight (FW) and seedling dry weight at 70°C for 24 hour (DW) were recorded. Seedling vigor index (SVI) was computed according to Abdul-Baki and Anderson (1973).

Data on ten germination and early seedling growth related parameters (GP, MDG, GIT, MGT, GDT, SL, RL, FW, DW, SVI) were subjected to analysis of variance using Statistix R computer software.

To study the genetic divergence of 29 genotypes, genetic analysis (Burton and De Vane, 1953; Zaki and Radwan, 2022) and multivariate analysis (Shah et al., 2018) were performed. Genetic analysis and multivariate analysis were performed using MS-Excel and IBM-SPSS computer programs. The coefficient of variability was calculated as per Singh and Chaudhary (1985). Heritability in broad sense was estimated as the ratio of genetic variance to the phenotypic variance according to Burton (1952) and categorized according to Robinson et al. (1949) to three classes: 0.0-30% (Low), 31-60% (Medium) and more than 60% (High).

The principal component analysis (PCA) was carried out using pooled mean of different traits under different genotypes following variability analysis of germination and early seedling growth related traits. The Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors represent the variance and the loadings of the corresponding principal components, respectively. Cluster analysis (CA) was used to group the genotypes into various clusters. Hierarchical clustering approach was used using Mahalanobis (Mahalanobis, 1928) generalized distance (D^2). Inter- and intra-cluster distances were computed using K-Mean clustering approach according to suggestions of Rao (1952).

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Selected Traits

The results of analysis of variance (ANOVA) of the collected data on different traits (Table not shown) showed highly significant F-ratio, which demonstrated the existence of variability among the linseed genotypes. The F-ratio for every trait was comparatively higher under salinity stress compared to control indicating substantial influence of stress environment in expression of phenotypic characters. Other investigators also reported similar findings linseed (Kumar and Kumar, 2020; Samantara et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2023).

Basic Variability Parameters

The descriptive statistics computed on the basis of adjusted mean values of ten quantitative traits depicted a wide range of phenotypic expressions for the germination and early seedling growth related traits. The mean values of GIT, MGT and GDT were lower but those of other 7 traits were considerably higher under control compared to salinity stress. The coefficient of variations percent (CV %) ranged from 4.70 to 32.76% under control and 3.06 to 23.39% under salinity stress (Table 1). The results revealed high levels of genotypic variation for the most basic variability traits of 29 linseed genotypes. The results are in agreement with other investigators (Kumar and Kumar, 2020; Samantara et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2023).

Genetic and Phenotypic Variability Parameters

Under control, both GCV and PCV were varied from 3.47-27.00% in all traits except GDT. The GCV and PCV were 22.61% and 39.80% respectively in GDT. Under salinity stress GCV and PCV were varied from 7.41 to 27.50% in 8 traits. In other two traits (SL and RL), GCV was 30.39% and 40.22% and PCV 31.65% to 41.59%, respectively (Table 2).

The broad sense heredity (H^2) ranged 14.76-93.58% under control and 27.66-97.21% under salinity stress. According to categorization scale of Robinson (1949), H^2 for FW, DW, SL, RL and SVI were high (more than 60%) under control as well as salinity stress. It was medium (32.26-43.2750 %) under control but high (78.85-97.21) under salinity stress for GP, MDG and MGT (Table 2).

The GCV and PCV were higher in GP, MDG, GIT, MGT, RL and SL but lower in GDT, DW and SVI under salinity stress compared to control. In general, the magnitude of PCV was higher compared to corresponding GCV for all traits under control as well as under salinity stress. The finding indicated the interaction of genotypes with environment. In other words, the environment (salinity) influenced the expression of these characters. Both GCV and PCV were low for GP, MDG, GIT, MGT, FW, DW and SVI under control as well as salinity stress indicating lower level of genetic variability among the genotypes in terms of these 7 parameters. High level of H^2 for FW, DW, SL, RL and SVI indicated that observed variations in the genotypes for germination related traits were mainly due to genetic factors. Other researchers also reported similar genetic variabilities (Kumari and Rao, 2008; Khan et al., 2013; Samantara et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2023).

Table 1. Basic Variability Parameters for Ten Germination and Early Seedling Growth Related Parameters of Linseed Under control and Salinity Stress

Trait	Under control (0 dS m ⁻¹)						Under salinity stress (average of 4, 8, 12 & 16 dS m ⁻¹)					
	Mean	Minimum	Minimum	Range	Std. Dev.	CV (%)	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Std. Dev.	CV (%)
GP	91.38	76.67	98.33	21.67	5.29	5.83	69.81	55.42	85.00	29.59	8.65	6.22
MDG	25.21	20.67	31.11	10.44	3.09	12.18	20.71	12.28	29.31	17.03	4.05	6.56
GIT	2.03	2.00	2.50	0.50	0.11	8.33	2.20	2.00	2.63	0.63	0.19	8.34
MGT	3.67	3.00	4.75	1.75	0.50	12.73	3.72	3.00	5.00	2.00	0.67	3.06
GDT	1.59	1.00	2.75	1.75	0.45	32.76	1.82	1.19	2.69	1.50	0.34	23.39
FW	0.71	0.52	0.89	0.37	0.10	4.70	0.48	0.31	0.62	0.31	0.08	6.52
DW	0.22	0.13	0.29	0.17	0.05	5.39	0.10	0.07	0.14	0.07	0.02	5.33
RL	3.55	2.05	5.18	3.13	0.87	12.83	2.43	1.27	3.76	2.49	0.75	8.85
SL	4.99	3.19	7.20	4.01	1.04	10.61	2.69	1.34	4.73	3.39	1.09	10.59
SVI	20.00	11.78	28.86	17.09	0.12	8.09	7.51	4.63	11.27	6.64	0.55	7.90

Abbreviations GP=Final germination percentage, MDG=Mean daily germination (%),GIT=Germination initial time (days), MGT=Maximum germination time (days), GDT=Germination duration time (days), FW=Seedling fresh weight (mg), DW= Seedling dry weight (mg), RL=Seedling root length (cm), SL=Seedling shoot length, SVI=Seedling vigor index, CV%=Coefficient of variation. *. Significant (P<0.05). F=F-Ratio, CV(%)=Coefficient of variation

Table 2. Genetic diversity statistics of ten quantitative traits of linseed genotypes under control and salinity stress

Trait	Under control (dS m ⁻¹)					Salinity stress (average of 4, 8, 12 and 16 dS m ⁻¹)				
	V _G	V _P	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	H ² (%)	V _G	V _P	GCV (%)	PCV (%)	H ² (%)
Germination percentage	20.895	49.244	5.00	7.68	42.43	70.193	89.033	12.00	13.52	78.85
Mean daily germination (%)	7.195	16.629	10.64	16.17	43.27	15.946	17.792	19.28	20.37	89.63
Germination initial time (days)	0.005	0.034	3.47	9.03	14.76	0.027	0.060	7.41	11.16	44.08
Maximum germination time (days)	0.200	0.419	12.19	17.62	47.84	0.450	0.463	18.04	18.29	97.21
Germination duration time (days)	0.130	0.403	22.61	39.80	32.26	0.069	0.250	14.47	27.50	27.66
Seedling fresh weight (mg)	0.010	0.012	14.37	15.12	90.32	0.006	0.007	16.27	17.53	86.16
Seedling dry weight (mg)	0.002	0.002	20.57	21.27	93.58	0.000	0.000	14.72	15.65	88.40
Seedling root length (cm)	0.713	0.921	23.76	27.00	77.44	0.545	0.591	30.39	31.65	92.18
Seedling shoot length (cm)	1.009	1.289	20.13	22.76	78.26	1.172	1.253	40.22	41.59	93.52
Seedling vigor index	20.330	22.947	22.54	23.95	88.59	2.346	2.698	20.41	21.88	86.97

Abbreviations. V_G= Genotypic variance, V_P= Phenotypic variance, GCV= Genotypic coefficient of variation, PCV= Phenotypic coefficient of variation, H²= Heredity (Broad-sense)

Principal Component Analysis

The principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to determine genetic divergence of genotypes. Two scree plots formed in PCA under control and salinity stress were used to determine number of components contributing maximum towards the explained variances. The scree plots suggested retaining the first two principal components (PC) both under control and salinity stress. Under control, the highest Eigenvalue of 2.98 (57.69%) was obtained for PC1 and 1.89 (19.23%) for PC2. Since the Eigenvalues of these two components were greater than one, hence they were retained. The first two PCs together

accounted for 69.46% of the total variations present in linseed genotypes. More or less similar trends were observed in contribution towards variation by PC2s under salinity stress where the highest Eigenvalue of 2.81 (46.81%) was obtained for PC1 and 1.12 (18.73%) for PC2. The first two components together explained 65.54% of total variances under salinity stress (Table 3 and Fig. 1A&B).

The findings revealed that the differentiation of genotypes into different components might be due to relatively high contribution of MGT, GDT, SVI and GPder control. Different characters have different loadings on the PCs. Most of the characters load on PC1 and only two of the characters were found to load on PC2. Accordingly, the PC1 had high positive component loading from MGT, GDT, SVI and GP under control. Similar trends were also found under salinity stress, where MGT, GDT, GIT and DW were the major contributors in PC1, and RL and SL contributed most to PC2. Such variations in PCs under control and salinity stress may be attributed to influence of salinity on germination related parameters (Table 3).

In the present investigation, high salinity level was found to cause impairment of germination and early seedling growth. The impairment might be attributed to the disruption in the normal functions of genetic characteristics of the affected genotypes. Similar results have been reported by many other investigators (Kaya et al., 2012; Pervez et al., 2021; Yasar and Yetssin, 2023). They reported that high salinity caused disruption or destruction of inherent germination capability and early seedling growth of linseed genotypes. The negative effect of salinity on seed germination may be attributed to either prevention of water uptake by osmotic pressure or reduction in the seed viability index by making a toxic effect on embryo viability (Houle et al., 2001).

Cluster Analysis

Initially, hierarchical cluster analysis was performed where a dendrogram was plotted. Scree plot was drawn based on coefficients of agglomeration obtained from hierarchical cluster analysis. According to dendrogram (Fig. 2 A&B) and elbow of scree plot number of clusters was determined to six.

Under control, six clusters of the 29 genotypes were formed at the rescaled distance (Euclidean distance) on the basis of Word Linkage clustering method. Cluster I contained the maximum number of 9 genotypes, and Cluster II, III and V contained 5 genotypes each. Cluster IV and cluster VI were consisted of 3 and 2 genotypes, respectively. Under salinity stress, the 29 genotypes also formed 6 clusters at the rescaled distance (Euclidean distance) on the basis of Word Linkage clustering technique. Cluster III contained the maximum number of 9 genotypes followed by cluster IV which contained 7 genotypes. Cluster II was consisted of 4 genotypes, and cluster I, V and VI contained 3 genotypes each (Fig. 2A&B and Table 4).

Variations in the responses of linseed genotypes to salinity stress in terms of intra- and inter-cluster distances were observed in the present investigation. Under control, the highest intra-cluster distance was found in cluster III (3.79) followed by cluster IV (3.25). The lowest intra-cluster distance was found in cluster II (2.39) followed by cluster V (2.68) and cluster VI (2.95). Under salinity stress, the highest intra-cluster distance (3.80) was recorded from cluster IV followed by cluster I (3.57), while the lowest intra-cluster distance was found in cluster VI (1.69) followed by cluster II (2.68) (Table 4).

Under control, the maximum inter-cluster distance (20.79) was noticed between clusters I and VI followed by the distance (15.29) between Cluster V and VI. The minimum inter-cultural distance (5.42) was observed between Clusters III and V followed by inter-cluster between cluster II and V (6.65). Under salinity stress, the highest inter-cluster distance (25.99) was observed between Cluster I and VI followed by the distance between clusters V and VI, while the lowest inter-cluster distance (8.79) was noticed between Cluster III and IV (Table 5).

The findings of the present investigation revealed that the intra-cluster distances within a cluster were comparatively low, which indicated that genetically closely related genotypes have been aggregated in the

same cluster. Kumar et al. (2018) reported that low intra-cluster distance (D^2 value) is the indication of little divergence from one genotype to another within a cluster. There are very low chances of obtaining satisfactory recombinants in segregating generations by crossing between the members of the same clusters.

The inter-cluster distances were comparatively higher than intra-cluster distances under control as well as under salinity stress. According to Patel et al. (2023), presence of higher inter-cluster distances than intra-cluster distances are the indications of existence of high genetic diversity among the genotypes. Thus, crossing of genotypes from these distantly related clusters may produce higher amount of heterotic expression in F1's and wide range of variability in subsequent segregations. Ananda and Murty (1968) also proposed hybridization between lines belonging to clusters separated by long inter-cluster distance in linseed. Presently, plant breeders are in the same opinions in case of hybridization programs of linseed (Kumar et al, 2018; Kumar and Kumar, 2020; Samantara et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2023), rice (Kumar et al., 2020;) and maize (Ahmad et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Contribution of Two Principal Components Under Control (A) and under Salt Stress (B)

Table 3. Principal Components Analysis of Six Quantitative Characters Showing Their Contributions Towards Total Variation among 29 Genotypes of Linseed under Control and Salt Stress Conditions

Traits studied	Control (0 dS m ⁻¹)		Salinity stress (average of 4, 8, 12 and 16 ds m ⁻¹)	
	PC1	PC2	PC1	PC2
Maximum germination time (days)	0.93*	-0.04	0.89*	-0.16
Germination duration time (days)	0.84*	-0.09	0.87*	0.217
Seedling vigor index	0.77*	-0.06	0.78*	-0.38
Germination percentage (%)	0.76*	0.22	0.62*	-0.39
Seedling root length (cm)	-0.07	0.94*	0.00	0.85*
Seedling shoot length (cm)	0.06	0.94*	-0.21	0.49*
Eigenvalue (Total)	2.98	1.89	2.81	1.12
Proportional variation (%)	49.65	19.82	46.81	46.81
Cumulative variation (%)	49.65	69.46	18.73	65.54

*.Substantial contribution to total variance in the respective axes.

Figure 2. Dendrograms Showing Genetic Relationships among Twenty Nine Linseed Genotypes under Control (A) and Salinity Stress (B)

Table 4. Total Clusters and Genotypes Falling in Each Cluster under Control Conditions and under Salinity Stress Conditions

Cluster number	Number of genotypes	Name of the genotypes (0 dS m ⁻¹)
		Under control conditions (0 dS m⁻¹)
Cluster I	9	Neela, BD-7143, BD-10710, Lin-503, BD-10706, BD-10703, Lin-1507/2, Lin-V-18, BD-7141
Cluster II	5	Lin-C-16, BD-10707, BD_10704, Lin-2403, Chilhari
Cluster III	5	Lin-703, Lin-303, Lin-C-17, BD-10698, Lin_S_19
Cluster IV	3	BD-7146, Lin-1503/2, Lin-1903
Cluster V	5	BD-10708, Lin-1203, Lin-W-17, Lin-803, BD_7142
Cluster VI	2	Lin-1303, Lin-1403
		Under salinity stress (average of 4, 8, 12 & 16 dS m⁻¹)
Cluster I	3	BD-10698, BD-10703, Lin-1507/2
Cluster II	4	Lin-703, Lin-303, Lin-C-17, Lin-W-17
Cluster III	9	BD-10710, BD-10708, Lin-V-18, Lin_S_19, Lin-2403, Lin-803, Lin-1503/2, Chilhari, BD_7142
Cluster IV	7	BD-7146, Lin-503, Lin-C-16, BD-10707, BD_10704, BD-7141, Lin-1903
Cluster V	3	BD-7143, BD-10706, Neela
Cluster VI	3	Lin-1203, Lin-1303, Lin-1403

Under control, cluster mean for GP, MGT, DW and SVI ranged (79.17-95.11%), (3.17-4.22 days), (0.15-0.26 g) and (12.97-24.71), respectively showing the highest values in cluster 1 which contained highest number of genotypes. The highest mean for GP was found in cluster I, which was statistically similar to cluster II and III. The cluster mean for GP in cluster IV and VI was statistically similar but significantly lower compared to other clusters. The highest MDG was recorded from cluster V, which was statistically similar to cluster IV but significantly lower compared to other clusters. Significantly the highest GIT was found in cluster IV. In other clusters, GIT was statistically similar. The seedling dry weigh was the highest in cluster II, which was statistically similar to other three clusters. Statistically similar SVI was recorded from clusters II and IV, which was significantly higher, compared to clusters III and VI. The lowest SVI was found in cluster VI, which was statistically similar to cluster III (Table 6).

Table 5. Estimates of Average Intra- (underlined) and Inter-Cluster Distances of 29 Linseed Genotypes on the Basis Principal Component Analysis under Control Condition and Salinity Stress Condition

Cluster number	Cluster I	Cluster II	Cluster III	Cluster IV	Cluster V	Cluster VI
Under control (0 dS m ⁻¹)						
Cluster I	<u>3.14</u>					
Cluster II	6.70	<u>2.39^b</u>				
Cluster III	12.44	8.23	<u>3.79^a</u>			
Cluster IV	13.83	7.92	11.49	<u>3.25</u>		
Cluster V	9.51	6.65	5.42*	10.18	<u>2.68</u>	
Cluster VI	20.79**	14.19	13.03	9.45	15.29	<u>2.95</u>
Under salinity stress (average of 4, 8, 12 & 16 dS m ⁻¹)						
Cluster I	<u>3.57</u>					
Cluster II	16.19	<u>2.68</u>				
Cluster III	9.83	9.30	<u>3.31</u>			
Cluster IV	21.97	9.08	12.41	<u>3.80^a</u>		
Cluster V	9.80	17.51	8.79*	19.32	<u>3.08</u>	
Cluster VI	25.99**	10.14	17.55	7.37	25.37**	<u>1.69^b</u>

Note: **.Maximum values and *. Minimum values

Table 6. Mean Values of Clusters for Some Germination and Early Seedling Growth Characters of Linseed Genotypes under Control and Salinity Stress

Cluster number	Germination percentage %	Mean daily germination %	Germination initial time (days)	Maximum germination time (days)	Seedling dry weight (g)	Seedling root length (cm)	Seedling shoot length (cm)	Seedling vigor index
under control (0 dS m ⁻¹)								
Cluster I	97.50	24.21	2.00	4.13	0.28	3.61	5.28	27.01
Cluster II	94.50	22.48	2.05	4.18	0.25	3.21	4.62	23.48
Cluster III	90.00	24.03	2.00	3.69	0.18	3.99	5.26	15.83
Cluster IV	83.33	26.11	2.17	3.17	0.25	2.76	3.99	21.13
Cluster V	92.70	29.15	2.05	3.22	0.19	3.64	4.94	17.31
Cluster VI	79.17	25.14	2.00	3.25	0.16	4.05	5.58	12.97
Under salinity stress (average of 4, 8, 12 & 16 dS m ⁻¹)								
Cluster I	81.53	27.27	2.02	3.08	0.10	2.17	2.35c	8.25
Cluster II	65.94	24.42	2.05	3.09	0.08	3.36	4.36	5.95
Cluster III	73.89	21.18	2.26	3.78	0.10	1.81	1.83	7.81
Cluster IV	62.44	16.5	2.28	4.14	0.11	2.34	2.40	7.16
Cluster V	81.39	17.93	2.40	4.71	0.13	2.68	3.03	10.51
Cluster VI	56.67	20.37	2.04	3.02	0.09	3.26	3.74	5.74

Under salinity stress, GP, MDG, MGT, DW and SVI varied (56.67-81.53%), (16.50-27.27%), (3.02-4.71 days), (0.08-0.13 g) and (5.74-10.51), respectively showing the maximum values in cluster I or V. The lengths of root and shoot in different clusters ranged (2.76-4.05 cm) and (3.99-5.58 cm) under control and (1.81-2.68 cm) and (1.83-4.36 cm) under stress condition. The cluster mean for GP in cluster I and V was statistically similar but significantly higher compared to other clusters. The lowest mean was recorded from cluster 6, which was statistically similar to cluster IV. The maximum mean for MDG was observed in cluster I, which was statistically similar to cluster II but significantly higher compared to other clusters. Mean dry weight in clusters I, III, IV, and V was statistically similar but significantly higher compared to only cluster II. The highest SVI was found in cluster V, which was statistically similar to

cluster I but significantly higher compared to other clusters. The lowest cluster means SVI was recorded from cluster VI, which was not significantly different from cluster III (Table 6).

The comparison of cluster means showed considerable differences among the clusters of different traits under control and salinity stress. In general, GP, MDG, DW, RL, SL and SVI were comparatively higher but GIT and MGT were lower under control than salinity stress. Such decreasing and increasing trends in germination characters might be attributed to adverse effect of salinity on phenotypic expression as reported by other investigators (Kaya et al., 2012; Day et al., 2018). The results of present investigation showed a wide diversity from one cluster to another in respect of cluster means for different traits indicating distinctly different mean performance of genotypes for different traits. The findings are in agreement with many other investigators who worked with linseed (Kumar and Kumar, 2020; Samantara et al., 2020; Patel et al., 2023) and rice (Kumar et al., 2020).

Conclusions

- The results of the present investigation revealed that the F-ratio was highly significant for all traits studied signifying the existence of genotypic variability among the genotypes. The F-ratio of ANOVA for every trait was comparatively higher under salinity stress compared to control indicating substantial influence of salt stress on environment in expression of phenotypic characters.
- Close association between phenotypic and genotypic coefficients of variability were recorded in the present investigation, which indicated the existence of sufficient genetic variability among the tested linseed genotypes.
- Based on the genetic divergence for germination and early seedling growth related traits, the 29 linseed genotypes were classified into six non-overlapping clusters under normal and salinity stress, which suggested considerable amount of genetic diversity in the materials. Under control, cluster I contained the maximum number of 9 genotypes, while in saline condition Cluster III contained the highest number of 9 genotypes.
- Under control, the maximum inter-cluster distance was noticed between clusters I and VI followed by the distance between Cluster V and VI. Under salinity stress, the highest inter-cluster distance was observed between Cluster I and VI followed by the distance between clusters V and VI. The results suggested that genotypes within these most distantly related clusters could be used as parents in hybridization program to develop desirable linseed variety because crosses between divergent genotypes generates heterotic segregates.
- Finally, it may be concluded that preliminary screening of linseed genotypes at early seedling growth stage based on fresh and dry weights, root and shoot lengths and vigor index of seedlings may be effective for the development of salt tolerant variety of linseed.

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